

iJEResearch

International Journal of Education and Research
Vol-1, Number 1, April - 2022 | Peer-Reviewed Journal
ISSN 27649733 | ijerresearch.org
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10592606

THE INSERTION OF LIBRAS IN THE EDUCATIONAL CONTEXT: THE POSSIBILITIES OF IMPLEMENTATION IN THE INITIAL YEARS AND IN THE NATIONAL EXAMINATION OF HIGH EDUCATION

AUTHORS

Ronaldo do Nascimento Carvalho - Post Doctorate in Administration by UNIBE/PY; PhD in Education Sciences from the Columbia University of Paraguay and Master in the Graduate Program in Non-Closed Cultural Territories and Expressions (TECCER).

Valeska Regina Soares Marques - Post doctoral in Public Health, Administrative Coordinator APAE Niterói, Teacher at the Institute IEP.

ABSTRACT

This article brings about the insertion of Libras in the educational context, with a possibility of implementation in the early years and the National Secondary Education Examination (ENEM), in which it is part of the curricular teaching proposals, however, the language is not inserted of signs, making it relevant for the development of learning and even for hearing and deaf children, with the aim of a permanent construction at school, which needs to be valued in order to establish a democratic and inclusive environment. The general aim was to analyze the inclusion of Libras in the initial years and in the national exam of secondary education as an important instrument in the educational context. Methodologically, this article had a qualitative approach and bibliographical research, contextualizing through articles, books, legislation, academic works, and important subjects that lead to understanding about the insertion of pounds in the initial years and in the national exam of secondary education as a mere important instrument in the educational context. Therefore, it is concluded that some do not include Sign Language as a subject in basic education, especially in PNC. However, observing the DCN, it is noted that its guidelines bring about Libras in a different way, in which they promote it as an important sign language for the integration and inclusion of hearing and deaf people. Despite these instruments not being very effective, it is analyzed that it shows the possibility of implementation for this teaching.

Keywords: Educational context. Pounds. Early Years. National High School Exam.

INTRODUCTION

The process of Libras's insertion in the educational context was an important perspective of creation throughout Brazil, giving as a referred instrument that arose from the need for communication of deaf people. In view of the initial years and the ENEM, it is part of the teaching curriculum proposals, however, sign language is not inserted, in which it is relevant for the development of learning and even for hearing children, to of a permanent construction in the school, which needs to be valued in order to establish a democratic and inclusive environment. Therefore, the justification for this theme emerged from preliminary investigations and shared experiences in the school community, in which Libras in the educational context is an instrument that has a valuable role for deaf individuals and teachers. Also, enabling and implementing it in the ENEM curriculum and in the initial years, this practice will bring a marked difference in educational policies, mainly linguistic, due to the inclusion and respect for Law nº 10.436/2002. Based on this assumption, the issue at hand is why the inclusion of Libras in the early years and in the national exam of secondary education is important for the educational context.

This research intends, as a general aim, to analyze the inclusion of Libras in the initial years and in the national exam of secondary education as an important instrument in the educational context. As for the specific objectives, they are to understand the importance of Libras in the educational context; understand the documents of Brazilian educational policies and Libras; discuss about the possibilities of implementing Libras in the initial years and in the National High School Examination.

Methodologically, throughout this article a qualitative approach and bibliographical research were used, contextualizing through articles, books, legislation, academic works, and important subjects that lead to understanding about the insertion of Libras in the initial years and in the national exam of secondary education as a mere important instrument in the educational context.

This article is divided into three sections, the first of which is about the importance of Libras in the educational context, which through its instrument makes several individuals in the school environment

have their communication of development in learning. The second section elaborated on the documents of Brazilian educational policies and Libras, which show the relevance of stimulating learning in the most accessible way in educational institutions, seeking approaches permeated in new learning. The third brings about the possibilities of implementing Libras in the early years and in the National High School Examination, considering the best succinct way to start the teaching stage.

Therefore, the relevance of this article stems from the question of the insertion of Libras aimed at establishing the knowledge present in the early years of elementary school and in ENEM, which will bring a present focus on communication between listeners and the deaf, and citizens.

THE IMPORTANCE OF LIBRAS IN THE EDUCATIONAL CONTEXT

From French Sign Language, Brazilian Sign Language emerged, starting in Brazil, the first school for the deaf, in 1856, with the support of D Pedro II and the collaboration of the French teacher of the deaf Eduard Huet. In 1857, in Rio de Janeiro, the Collégio Nacional for Deaf-Mutes, currently the National Institute of Education for the Deaf (INES), was founded, in which he began to teach students who lived in that city. In fact, in the 1980s, this language, through the Bill, became legalized and recognized by Law No. 10,436 on April 24, 2002.

Deafness has always been considered, as well as any disability, a curse that threw the man into limbo or death for identifying him as incapable. And this, for not resembling the normality grouped in time and space, is not only excluded by the spiritual context but also by the economic partner in different cultures, as Duarte explains (2013, p. 1715), "knowledge and reflection on the spaces and times that shaped the history of the deaf – ranging from sacrifices in public squares, reclusion in institutions, integrationist policies to current discourses of inclusion".

Costa (2022) emphasizes that "Law 10.436/2002, which makes Libras official as an official language and gives the Deaf person the right to have a quality education, brings out the importance of teaching Libras in the early years of the Deaf child",

enabling educational and social inclusion, due to its integration with the language itself, which facilitates learning and communication in this environment.

Soon, then, through Decree nº 5.626, of December 22, 2005, the inclusion of Libras was inserted as a curricular subject for the deaf community, with Portuguese as a second language, as well as the training of bilingual teachers, among other aspects, making it clear that this instrument in the educational context has become important for inclusive practices, both in schools and in society, providing the cognitive and linguistic development of all individuals with deafness, in order to facilitate the learning process (BAIENSE; SILVA, 2022).

In this way, Libras are placed as a form of language that promotes social inclusion and communication in society for individuals with deafness. Its importance in the school environment must be highlighted, as it allows these subjects to have acceptance and development in learning, guaranteeing the preservation of their community through this language. Therefore, in the educational context, this language enables people to communicate in the social environment, developing their professional and educational skills.

ANALYSIS OF BRAZILIAN EDUCATIONAL POLICY DOCUMENTS AND LIBRAS

As previously seen, Libras focuses on the obligation of the most varied curricular disciplines, within the context of the needs of deaf and hearing people. Reflecting on education brings a direction for learning, as well as determinations that are listed in the modality brought by the National Curriculum Parameters - PNC. This document had its reflexive changes, in which it institutes linguistic recognition. As the PNC determines that:

Obligatorily to provide opportunities for the study of the Portuguese language, mathematics, the physical and natural world, and the social and political reality, emphasizing knowledge of Brazil. The teaching of Art and Physical Education are also compulsory curricular areas, necessarily integrated into the pedagogical proposal. The teaching of

at least one modern foreign language becomes a mandatory curricular component, from the fifth grade of elementary school onwards (PNC, 1997, p.14).

The PNC does not have information on the teaching of Sign Languages; however, this document is attached to the other languages for teaching, discussing the National Curriculum Guidelines - DCN, in which it adds Law nº 9.795/99, providing for the National Policy of Environmental Education and Law No. 10,436/2002, which provides for the Brazilian Sign Language (LIBRAS). In view of this, the guidelines present special needs, bringing the language of Libras in a different way. According to inc. 3, students must have access to its contents, “through the use of applicable languages and codes, such as the Braille system, the Brazilian Sign Language (LIBRAS) and assistive technology [...]” (BRASIL, 2013, p. 407).

The Law of Guidelines and Bases - LDB also states that it will be “given in Portuguese, assured to indigenous communities and the use of their mother tongues and learning processes” (BRASIL, 1996). In this way, the insertion of Libras became one of the perspectives for the use of interpreters, teachers, among others, in which it evidenced, among other languages, the communication between hearing and deaf people, passing as a form of visual language based on hand gestures. and body and facial expression, which leads thousands of people to want to understand and learn Sign Language, to exchange experiences, aiming at integration and inclusion between hearing and deaf people.

THE POSSIBILITIES OF IMPLEMENTING LIBRAS IN THE INITIAL YEARS AND IN THE NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL EXAMINATION

In 1998, the ENEM was instituted, aiming to evaluate the school performance of students during the end of basic education, which, in 2009, was improved with a new methodology, starting to use mechanisms for access to higher education. Since then, in 2020, the participant has chosen to take the printed or digital exam, applying tests through computers, in institutions defined by the National Institute of Educational Studies and Research Anísio Teixeira - Inep.

With this, it is verified how recent this Decree is, as stated by Kumada and Pietro (2019, p. 81), “after the regulation of Libras and the establishment of the training of professionals to teach this language system, reality still reflects a great need in the area”. The Enem is also administered in Libras for the deaf and hearing-impaired community who only have Libras as their first language, in which the participant needs to request the appeal via video test with an additional time of up to 120 minutes on each day of the test. On the other hand, this evaluation for the listeners is not inserted as a discipline, making it clear that it presents a lack of inclusion for the knowledge of the listeners. Above all, these issues become relevant to expand learning in educational institutions, aiming at the integration of this language dynamics for all individuals. Soon,

The important thing, therefore, is that students appropriate the specificities of each language, without losing sight of the whole in which they are inserted. More than that, it is important that they understand that languages are dynamic and that everyone participates in this process of constant transformation (BRASIL, 2018, p. 63).

Understanding how ENEM proposes its assessment methods contributes to a perspective that should be revised, inserting a national policy to measure students’ knowledge following education guidelines, in an idealized margin that involves all disciplines, including sign language. When referring to the early years of elementary school, this language should also be considered essential for learning. In view of this, enabling this implementation in these stages may constitute an expansion in the interaction of languages between hearing and deaf people.

The reinvention of the ENEM as a selective process to replace the entrance exam would support and help democratize access to the university, which, together with the subsequent system of the quota program, would allow the inclusion of different social groups and the expansion of higher education services. This, therefore, would make the Enem an ambivalent instrument, being used whether at the entrance to technical or higher-level courses and

at the same time also used to assess the skills and abilities acquired by students at the secondary level. In the Incorporation of the function of admitting and distributing vacancies in public and private universities, ENEM promotes the modification of cultural subjectivity, in economic and social relations, as well as re-elaborates a common base of norms and content for High School (PIAIA, 2013). Therefore, based on this understanding, there is a mistake in documents about Libras, which is a mother tongue that should be recognized as a school subject, which could be inserted in the early years of elementary school and ENEM, along with the other languages, and not as a playful method of gestures, while there is a need for expansion in learning.

CONCLUSION

To conclude this article, it is known that Libras is an important instrument in educational institutions, officially, a sign language that is proposed for hearing and deaf people, which mediates the communication between both, which, relatively, is considered an evolution that empowers individuals across the country. Among the other questions about this research, it is understood that this sign language is of fundamental relevance for teachers, therefore, its implementation process in the initial years and in ENEM, overcomes a great challenge for those working in this inclusive space.

Thus, it is noted that the importance of Libras in the educational context revolves around a discipline that must be fundamental in the school environment, considering it as an instrument that is available in legislation, being created to facilitate communication in the educational context, as well as, a horizon that can go far beyond a normal path, since learning this language provides the school community with an interactivity that emphasizes the appreciation of deaf people, providing opportunities for communicative interaction between teachers, students, and citizens.

After analyzing the Brazilian educational policies and Libras, it is concluded that some do not insert Sign Language as a subject of basic education, mainly the PNC. However, observing the DCN, it is noted that its guidelines bring about Libras in a different way, in which they promote it as an

important sign language for the integration and inclusion of hearing and deaf people. Despite these instruments not being very effective, it is analyzed that it shows the possibility of implementation for this teaching.

REFERENCES

COSTA, Letícia Gomes. A importância do ensino da LIBRAS na educação Infantil. Orientadora: Ana Cleide Vieira Gomes Guimbal de Aquino. 2022. 16 f. Monografia (Especialização em Educação Especial e Inclusão Socioeducacional) - Universidade Federal Rural da Amazônia, Campus Belém, PA, 2022.

BAIENSE, Joyce Karolina Ribeiro; SILVA, Rafael Monteiro da. A importância da formação docente para a educação de surdos nos ambientes educacionais. 2022. Disponível em: <https://multivix.edu.br/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/revista-espaco-academico-v12-n02-artigo10.pdf>. Acesso em: 05 mar. 2023.

BRASIL. Ministério da Educação. Secretaria de Educação Básica. Secretaria de Educação Continuada, Alfabetização, Diversidade e Inclusão. Secretaria de Educação Profissional e Tecnológica. Conselho Nacional da Educação. Câmara Nacional de Educação Básica. Diretrizes Curriculares Nacionais Gerais da Educação Básica. Secretaria de Educação Básica. Diretoria de Currículos e Educação Integral. Brasília: MEC, SEB, DICEI, 2013.

BRASIL. Secretaria de Educação Fundamental. Parâmetros curriculares nacionais: introdução aos parâmetros curriculares nacionais/Secretaria de Educação. Brasília: MEC/SEF, 1997.

BRASIL. Diretrizes e Bases da Educação Nacional. Lei nº 9.394, de 20 de dezembro de 1996. Estabelece as diretrizes e bases da educação nacional. Disponível em: https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Leis/L9394.htm. Acesso em: 05 mar. 2023.

BRASIL. Ministério da Educação. Base Nacional Comum Curricular. Língua Portuguesa. Brasília: MEC/SEE. 2018. Disponível em: <http://basenacionalcomum.mec.gov.br>. Acesso em: 05

mar. 2023.

DUARTE, S. B. R et al. Aspectos históricos e socioculturais da população surda. *História, Ciências, Saúde-Manguinhos*, v. 20, n. 4, p. 1713-1734, 2013.

KUMADA, K. M. O.; PRIETO, R. G. Desdobramentos da política de educação superior para formação do docente de libras. *Cadernos de pesquisa*, São Paulo, v. 49, n. 173, p. 64-84, 2019.

PIAIA, K. et al. Política avaliativa do ENEM: pressupostos da qualidade social da educação? 131f. Dissertação da Universidade de Passo Fundo, 2013. Disponível em: <http://tede.upf.br/jspui/bitstream/tede/790/1/2013KarinePiaia.pdf>. Acesso em: 05 mar. 2023.